

Questionnaire

Consequences of antibiotic overuse in Saudi Arabia: A multidimensional analysis

Section 1: Demographic Information

1. **What is your gender?**
 - Male
 - Female
 2. **What is your age group?**
 - 18-29
 - 30-39
 - 40-49
 - 50 and above
 3. **What is your highest level of education?**
 - High school or below
 - Diploma
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - Doctoral degree
 4. **What is your current occupation?**
 - Doctor
 - Nurse
 - Pharmacist
 - Patient/General Public
 - Other (please specify)
 5. **Which region do you live in?**
 - Central
 - Western
 - Eastern
 - Northern
 - Southern
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Section 2: Awareness and Knowledge of Antibiotic Use

6. **Are you aware that antibiotic overuse can lead to antibiotic resistance?**
 - Yes
 - No
7. **Do you think antibiotics are effective against viral infections (e.g., cold, flu)?**
 - Yes

- No
 - 8. **How often do you or your patients request antibiotics for non-bacterial infections like colds or flu?**
 - Always
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
 - 9. **Do you think public awareness about antibiotic resistance is sufficient in your region?**
 - Yes
 - No
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Section 3: Antibiotic Prescription and Use Practices

10. **How often do you prescribe/take antibiotics?**

- Very often
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

11. **Have you ever used antibiotics without a prescription?**

- Yes
- No

12. **How likely are you to complete the full course of antibiotics when prescribed?**

- Very likely
- Likely
- Unlikely
- Never

13. **Have you ever stopped taking antibiotics before completing the prescribed course?**

- Yes
- No

14. **Do you believe over-prescribing antibiotics contributes to antibiotic resistance?**

- Yes
- No

Section 4: Perceptions of Antibiotic Resistance and Healthcare Costs

15. Do you believe antibiotic-resistant infections are harder to treat than non-resistant ones?

- Yes
- No

16. In your opinion, how serious is the issue of antibiotic resistance in your region?

- Very serious
- Somewhat serious
- Not serious

17. Do you think antibiotic overuse increases healthcare costs?

- Yes
- No

18. Do you believe stronger regulations on antibiotic prescriptions are necessary to combat resistance?

- Yes
- No

19. What are the main reasons for antibiotic overuse in your experience? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of awareness
- Patient demand
- Self-medication
- Easy access to antibiotics
- Other (please specify)

Section 5: Public Health Recommendations

20. Do you think public health campaigns are effective in reducing unnecessary antibiotic use?

- Yes
- No

21. Would you support stricter regulations on over-the-counter sales of antibiotics?

- Yes
- No

22. What strategies do you believe would be most effective in reducing antibiotic overuse? (Select all that apply)

- Increased public awareness
- Stricter prescription regulations
- Improved healthcare professional training
- Monitoring and auditing of antibiotic prescriptions
- Development of new antibiotics